

Directing Volunteer Work to Achieve the Well-Being of University Students (Youth), to Ensure Collective Health

Aida Albasalah, Samar Alshawwa, Razan Alarnous

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 09 , 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Collective Health, University students, Volunteer work, Volunteering</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5500495</p>	<p><i>Volunteers often represent the soul and heart of a group, performing tasks and providing services that keep the group functional and productive. Several groups have less paid staff than volunteers. Structured questionnaire was administered to individuals associated with Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. 49 duly completed questionnaires were returned. The respondents were professionals within the ages of 25 and above 40 years. The general objective of this study is to assess the concept of volunteer work among university students (youth); assess various types of volunteer work; examine how directing volunteer work can achieve the well-being of university students (youth); examine how volunteer work ensures collective health. The results showed the benefits of volunteering which ranges from dissemination of culture, promotion of Islamic values and morals, enhancement of student's skills, community education and awareness of female students, coordination with training organizations and positive contribution to the society. It also revealed the reasons why participants (volunteers) opted to take part in volunteering. Social media, though used by most of the respondents, are utilized irregularly. The results also revealed the correlation between four axes of this study (first axis, second axis, third axis and fourth axis).</i></p>

Introduction

For a healthy society, volunteers are necessary and immensely helpful. Volunteers possess great deal of skills. Many are skilled professionals. Engineers, financial planners and medical doctorvolunteers, and also do students. People do donate their effort and time to different purposes, all day of the year. There is a great difference between paid staff and volunteers. The more associated with a society people feel, the more probable they are to be accountable to the society and have a sense of pride and dedication. Often, volunteers represent the soul and heart of a group, performing tasks and providing services that keep the group functional and productive. Several groups have less paid staff than volunteers. Volunteer programs are not entirely free. There must be investment of time and other resources to ensure the effectiveness of the volunteer. Volunteer programs are important investments for almost all organizations that have identified the importance of a program and have the willingness to undertake the sacrifice.

Young people and university students have the capacity to make significant inputs to a volunteer group. The organizations, the community, and the students derive benefits from community service where young people of school age volunteer. For several universities and schools, community service forms part of the requirements for students to complete their program and graduate. Eventually, some students may build up a lifelong commitment to community support. Furthermore, students that develop interest in community support may stimulate their parents to make time and financial contribution to such programs.

According to Davis Smith (1998, 1999), "there has been extensive study on the benefits of volunteering in population studies, demonstrating volunteering individual and societal benefits" augmented happiness (Borgonovi 2008), lessening of death rates (Musick *et al.* 1999); improvement of mental and physical well-being (life contentment, cheerfulness, confidence, physical health depression and sense of control over life,) (Thoits and Hewitt 2001) and decreased depressive symptoms (Reitschlin 1998). Nevertheless, the benefits of volunteer women themselves in Lay health volunteers (LHA) programs have not been widely studied. Feelings of ambivalent concerning women's volunteering, as a result of not being paid and supposed as possible mistreatment (Merrell 2000), are even more prominent concerning marginalized women, that obviously lack resources for volunteering (Tang 2006), but still decide to volunteer. Davis Smith (1999) opined "the absence of reliable information regarding volunteering benefits might relate to most unpaid work being less recognized, similar to women's unpaid housework". This upholds the unawareness of the benefits of volunteering and results to its being ignore in development of strategies towards financing volunteer-dependent civil groups.

Evaluating benefits will raise volunteering awareness concerning the social and economic contributions lay women make to their families, societies, and themselves.

Health is “a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity” (WHO, 1948). The gratification of the highest attainable standard of health is among the fundamental rights of all human beings. The health of every individual is essential to the achievement of peace and security and is dependent on the fullest collaboration of states and individuals.

Volunteering renders several benefits to both physical and mental health. The public contact aspect of working and helping volunteering can have an intense effect on a student’s total mental well-being. Volunteering helps in improving mood, reducing, anger anxiety and stress because there will be interactions with others.

Volunteering helps to protect against depression and create strong support system. Volunteering makes one happy. Researchers have revealed that providing help to others gives enormous pleasure. The more help we render, the happier become.

Volunteering improves self-confidence. Doing good to others and the society gives a sense of achievement. Your responsibility as a volunteer can also provide you a sense of identity and pride. The better you feel about yourself, the more likely you are to have an optimistic view of your life and prospective goals.

Volunteering can make people forget their worries, keep them mentally motivated, and add more gusto to their lives. It can also help one stay physically healthy.

The benefits of using volunteers are summarized in first of all increasing the ability to serve customers and respond to community needs like expanded operation time, shorter waiting time and increased services, better staff diversity such as race, age, social background, education and income, improved skill set, and finally extended societal support.

In regard to the roles of volunteer workers, several people perceive volunteers as assistants stopping by in their extra time to organize files, answer phones, or pay visit to sick people. Nonetheless, several groups in their onset depend largely on volunteers to perform the duties that are later performed by paid staff. Volunteers occupy a vital role in fund-raising, handling day-to-day tasks and running organizations. Some institutions might not exist without volunteers. Indeed, the committees and boards of local associations and agencies consist completely of volunteers. Bigger organizations, like the American Red Cross and the Salvation Army, have survived for over one hundred (100) years due in large part to a solid volunteer dedication (Musick *et al.* 1999). Several organizations depend on volunteers to carry out necessary, important tasks. Religion-based groups usually have volunteer religious school teachers, youth group leaders, and mentors. Congregations’ members may contribute time during the week to assist in maintaining the amenities and arrange programs. These volunteers are significant to the continued existence of organizations. Volunteers possess great deal of skills. Many are skilled professionals. Engineers, financial planners and medical doctors volunteer, and also do students. The tasks done by volunteers range widely, from preparing meals, translating materials for non-English speakers, and stuffing envelopes, to evaluation expertise, providing legal support, and medical care (Musick *et al.* 1999). They render clinical services; tutor, mentor, and train other volunteers and clients; and assist with organizational operations, like technical support. Indeed, volunteers assist building and strengthening our societies by responding to the requirements that make each society unique.

The objectives of this study are to assess the concept of volunteer work among university students (youth), assess various types of volunteer work; examine how directing volunteer work can achieve the well-being of university students (youth), and finally to examine how volunteer work ensures collective health.

Methodology

To facilitate the collection data for this study, a structured questionnaire was administered to individuals working at Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. 98 duly completed questionnaires were returned. The respondents were professionals within the ages of 25 and above 40 years.

The survey design included questions about socio-demographic characteristics, the importance of volunteer work from the point of view of those interested in student activity; the reasons for the existence of the phenomenon of unhealthy behavior on campus from the point of view of those interested in student activity; directing the volunteer efforts of those interested in student activity for early detection of unhealthy behavior at the university and setting up a mechanism to reduce it; and reasons for participation and assistance mechanism in the detection of non-health behavior at the university for those who actually participated from interested student activity

The data collected was statistically analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to report the frequencies and percentages for definite variables. Missing data were omitted on a basis analysis-by-analysis and valid percentages were reported. The data was also subjected to correlation analysis to determine the relationship between the four axes (expatiated in the *APPENDIX*).

Results:

The data collected through structured questionnaires were analyzed and represented in statistical tables and charts.

Table 1: Socio-demographical Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
25 - 29yrs	20	20.4
30 - 34yrs	38	38.8
35 - 39yrs	18	18.4
Above 40yrs	22	22.4
Total	98	100.0
Educational Level		
High School	6	6.1
Bachelor	44	44.9
Master	22	22.4
Doctorate	26	26.5
Total	98	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	18	18.4
Married	66	67.3
Divorced	12	12.2
Widow	2	2.0
Total	98	100.0
Profession		
Demonstrator	20	20.4
Administrative	34	34.7
Doctor	26	26.5
Lecturer	16	16.3
Partly Employee	2	2.0
Total	98	100.0

The socio-demographical characteristics of the respondents is represented in the table 1 above. Most (38.8%) of the respondents were within the age of 30 to 34 years; most of them (44.9%) has Bachelor degree. In terms of marital status, there were more married people (67.3%) while the least of the marital status is widow (2.0%). Most of the respondents had administrative profession (34.7%); this is followed by doctor (26.5%), demonstrator (20.4%), lecturer (16.3%) and the partly employee (2.0%) as represented in the table.

Figure 1: Activities

Practiced by Respondents

Figure 1: illustrates the various activities practiced by the respondents. 14.3% of the respondents practiced voluntary activities; 12.4%, 4.1% and 2.0% of the respondents practiced Social, Scientific and cultural activities respectively. Most of the respondents (42.9%) practiced both social and cultural activities. 4.1% of the respondents each practiced Social, Scientific & Cultural, Scientific & Cultural, and Scientific & Voluntary, and Training activities; while 8.2% of them practiced Social & Scientific activities.

Table 2: Benefits of Volunteering Activities

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Dissemination of culture, promote Islamic values and moral	10	10.2
Development of Student Skills	52	53.1
Benefit society and gain experience	8	8.2
Community education and awareness of female students/women	16	16.3
Coordination with training bodies	6	6.1
Total	92	93.9
Missing System	6	6.1
Total	98	100.0

Table 2 presents the benefit of volunteering especially to university students (youth) and to the society at large. A key benefit of volunteering as reported by the respondents is the development of student skills (53.1%). Learning of new skill set will help them advance their careers; this is followed by community education and awareness of female students/women (16.3%). This is usually achieved by connecting to the community and others thereby creating awareness on areas the community need enlightenment. Cultural dissemination and promotion of the Islamic values and moral (10.2%) is yet another benefit of volunteering. Coordination with training bodies/organizations (6.1%) is an avenue for volunteers to develop good management and administrative skills, thus it is real benefit to university students who engage in volunteering.

Table 3: Reasons that led you to accept the position and the tasks related to it:

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Implementation of the administration's desire	12	12.2
In order to gain experience and skill	22	22.4

In order to gain experience and skill + implementation of the administration desire	12	12.2
To provide the best for the campus community	2	2.0
In order to gain experience and skill + To provide the best for the campus community	6	6.1
Implementation of the administration's desire+ To provide the best for the campus community	12	12.2
Implementation of the admin desire/ In order to gain experience and skill / To provide the best for the campus community	20	20.4
Is it a national social duty	10	10.2
In implementation of the admin's desire, to provide the best for the campus community , it is a national societal duty	2	2.0
Total	98	100.0

Several reasons led respondents to accept certain positions and tasks related to it in volunteering. Table 3 out listed some of these reasons which include the need to gain experience and skills (22.4%); implementation of administration desire (12.2%); having the perception of volunteering been a national societal duty (10.2%); to provide the best for the campus community (2.0%). A combination of two or more of these reasons is stated in the above table.

Table 4: Do you use social media to market your unit?

	Frequency	Percent
Valid Yes	84	85.7
No	14	14.3
Total	98	100.0

Table 4 above shows the number of respondents who use social media to promote their unit or activities. 85.7% of the respondents use social media to advertise their activities or unit; the remaining 14.3% of them reported not to utilize social media in promoting their activities.

Table 5: Frequency of the used social media

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Intermittently	60	61.2
Always	20	20.4
Through Official Media	4	4.1
Total	84	85.7
Missing System	14	14.3
Total	98	100.0

From Table 5 above, and of the 84 (85.7%) who use social media to promote their unit/activities, 60(61.2%) of the respondents reported intermittent use of social media; this is followed by 20 (20.4%) who use social media on a regular basis; and 4(4.1%) reported going through official media channels under the umbrella of the enterprise and with each event, display screens are available in all colleges and institutes and students to promote voluntary activities.

Figure 2: The Most Common Social Networks Used in Promoting and Marketing

From Figure 2, it is observed that of all the respondents who use social media in promotion of their activities, a great chunk of them utilize WhatsApp (20.4%) in promoting their activities; this is followed by those who make use of a combination of Twitter, Phone calls, LinkedIn & WhatsApp (16.3%). 2%, 4.1% and 6.1% of the users of social media make use of Facebook, Twitter and SnapChat respectively. Others utilized are Twitter & LinkedIn (6.1%), Twitter & Telegram (2.0%), WhatsApp & Phonecalls (6.1%); Twitter, SnapChat & WhatsApp (8.2%); Twitter, SnapChat, Instagram & WhatsApp (6.1%); Twitter, LinkedIn & WhatsApp (2.0%); WhatsApp and Twitter (10.2%); WhatsApp & Telegram (2.0%); Twitter & Emails (6.1%); Twitter, SnapChat, Instagram, Phone calls, Youtube & WhatsApp (2.0%).

Table 6: Correlation between the First, Second, Third and Fourth axis Correlations

		FIRST_AXIS	SECOND_AXI S	THIRD_AXIS	FOURTH_AXI S
FIRST_AXIS	Pearson Correlation	1	0.030	0.811**	0.487**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.836	0.000	0.000
	N	98	98	98	98
SECOND_AXIS	Pearson Correlation	0.030	1	0.201	0.327*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.836		0.165	0.022
	N	98	98	98	98

THIRD_AXIS	Pearson Correlation	0.811**	0.201	1	0.592**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.165		0.000
	N	98	98	98	98
FOURTH_AXIS	Pearson Correlation	0.487**	0.327*	0.592**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.022	0.000	
	N	98	98	98	98

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

First axis: the importance of volunteer work from the point of view of those interested in student activity; **The second axis:** the reasons for the existence of the phenomenon of unhealthy behavior on campus from the point of view of those interested in student activity; **third axis:** directing the volunteer efforts of those interested in student activity for early detection of unhealthy behavior at the university and setting up a mechanism to reduce it. **Fourth axis:** Reasons for participation and assistance mechanism in the detection of non-health behavior at the university for those who actually participated from interested student activity.

From the table 6 above, the correlation between the first and second axis is 0.030 indicating a weak relationship between the importance of volunteer work from the point of view of those interested in student activity (first axis) and the reasons for the existence of the phenomenon of unhealthy behavior on campus from the point of view of those interested in student activity (second axis). The Sig. (2 tailed) is 0.836 indicating that there is a statistically significant correlation between the two variables.

Pearson correlation value of the first and third axis are strongly is 0.811 indicating positively strong correlation between the importance of volunteer work from the point of view of those interested in student activity (first axis) and directing the volunteer efforts of those interested in student activity for early detection of unhealthy behavior at the university and setting up a mechanism to reduce it (third axis). Thus, an increase in the value of the first variable (the first axis) will result to increase the value of the other variable (the third axis). The p-value is less than 0.05 indicating that there is no statistically significant correlation between the variables of the first and third axis.

There is a slightly weak correlation ($r = 4.87$) between the importance of volunteer work from the point of view of those interested in student activity (first axis) and reasons for participation and assistance mechanism in the detection of non-health behavior at the university for those who actually participated from interested student activity (fourth axis). There is no statistically significant correlation between the two variables (first and fourth axis) as p-value is less than 0.05.

There is a weak correlation ($r = 0.201$) between the reasons for the existence of the phenomenon of unhealthy behavior on campus from the point of view of those interested in student activity (second axis) and directing the volunteer efforts of those interested in student activity for early detection of unhealthy behavior at the university and setting up a mechanism to reduce it (third axis). P-value is 0.165 indicating that there is a statistically significant correlation between these two variables.

The correlation between the second and fourth axis is 0.327 indicating a weak relationship between “the reasons for the existence of the phenomenon of unhealthy behavior on campus from the point of view of those interested in student activity” and “the reasons for participation and assistance mechanism in the detection of non-health behavior at the university for those who actually participated from interested student activity”. The p-value is 0.022 indicating no statistically significant correlation between the two variables (second and fourth axis).

There is a moderate correlation ($r = 0.592$) between directing the volunteer efforts of those interested in student activity for early detection of unhealthy behavior at the university and setting up a mechanism to reduce it (third axis) and the reasons for participation and assistance mechanism in the detection of non-health behavior at the university for those who actually participated from interested student activity (fourth axis). The p-value is less than 0.05 indicating no statistically significant correlation between the two variables (third and fourth axis).

Figure 3(a)
r =

0.30; p-value = 0.836

Figure 3(b) $r = 0.811$; p-value = 0.00

Figure
3(c) $r =$
0.327; p-
value =
0.022

Figure

3(d) $r = 0.487$; p-value = 0.00

Figure
3(e) r
=
0.201;
p-value
=
0.165

Figure 3(f) $r = 0.592$; p-value = 0.00

Figure 3 (a) to (f) is a scatter plot of the considered variables. As seen, the data in figure (3b) shows an uphill pattern from left to right of the scatter plot of first axis relating third axis thus indicating a positively strong relationship between these two variables (first and third axis). This uphill pattern is somewhat seen in figure 3(d) and 3(f) showing a positive relationship between the first and fourth axis and the third and fourth axis respectively. There is no relationship between the variables in figure 3(a), 3(c) and 3(e).

Discussion

Adults are for the most part motivated to volunteer by association or the need to connect with others. This is in cognizance of the work of Henderson (2018) on volunteerism – motivation and perceptions. Observers and academic researchers are often intrigued by the reasons why people volunteer as majority of volunteering organization do not offer monetary benefit to volunteers. These volunteers are motivated by one or more non-monetary benefits like self-satisfaction in contributing to the wellbeing of the society, dissemination of culture and promotion of the Islamic values and moral, development of skills. This is in line with Cnaan & Goldberg-Glen (1991) whose findings revealed two dominate motivates for volunteering – utilitarian and altruistic motivations.

Just as presented in the work of Waters (2010), in this study social media aided in promotion of activities/units of volunteer organizations since social media like whatsapp, twitter, instagrams and the likes make available more than enough chances for these organizations to increase their community presence and impact. Generally, students who are involved in volunteering activities are unlikely to be involved in unhealthy behavior (Kohut,

1998; Hall, 1999). On the contrary, they play leadership roles in bringing offenders to book and in the early detection of unhealthy behavior thus controlling and reducing unhealthy behavior among university students.

Volunteers receive persons coming for treatment as well as their families, provide them with information, and make them relax; assist with events, media relations, medical records, fundraising, awareness programs and community outreach, and in-service training; and at times carry out medical jobs in treatment programs.

In transitional housing and residential treatment settings, volunteers act as house administrators, render child care to children while their parents are in groups, take customers to schedule with doctors, and take children to schools. Volunteers working in prisons and jails programs render group and individual counseling, education on addiction and recovery, life skills classes and vocational training, as well as relapse prevention groups, lead parenting, and anger management.

Volunteers, sometimes, render services in the aspect of landscaping, making sure that there is an attractive place for healing. Wenger (2004) states that, "a trained, skilled and committed volunteer has always been a piece of gold for cash-strapped non-profit organizations, including treatment programs".

For instance, Samaritan Village, a non-profit group in New York running seven (7) drug-free housing facilities, has employed volunteers' skills to lessen the overwhelming effects of substance abuse on communities, families, and individuals for over one generation. Volunteers have brought spontaneous and fresh passion, a willing and cheerful spirit, as well as a lasting dedication to the mission of the Samaritan Village.

Project H.O.P.E is another treatment program that depends profoundly on volunteers. It is a substance abuse and HIV/AIDS deterrence program aiming Hispanic and African American women at risk for sexually transmitted diseases, including HIV, and drug addiction (Wenger, 2004). Volunteers at this Washington, DC, program offer a wide array of invaluable services, including developing prevention gears and motivations for programmed events; assisting with child care, transportation, and mental health services; serving as chaperones for youth retreats; producing a quarterly newsletter; helping with program referrals; acting as household violence and anger management training facilitators and serving as advisors to the Board of Directors and STEPS Volunteer Program.

Other prevention, treatment, and recovery groups call upon musicians who have been affected by drug or alcohol addiction to speak or entertain at program completion activities, fundraisers and alumni activities. Musician volunteers pass a strong message to young adults about the benefits of a substance-free life via live performances, action programs and education.

Conclusion

The results showed that the benefits of volunteering which ranges from dissemination of culture, promotion of Islamic value and morals, enhancement of student skills, community education and awareness of female students, coordination with training organizations and positive contribution to the society. It also revealed the reasons why participants (volunteers) opted to take part in volunteering. Social media, though used by most of the respondents, are utilized irregularly. The results also revealed the correlation between four axes of this study (first axis, second axis, third axis and fourth axis).

Abbreviations

Not applicable.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Ethics approval was obtained for this study from the International Review Board (IRB) in Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Any raw data or materials used in the preparation of this manuscript are available upon reasonable request to Dr. Samar Alshawwa (samarzuhair@yahoo.com)

Competing of interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contribution

All authors were responsible for the initiation, conceptualization and leadership of the guideline development process. AA and SA were responsible for the respondent's survey. RA and SA were responsible for the data statistical analysis and interpretation of results. AA was the primary author of the manuscript. All coauthors

were responsible for writing, reviewing, and revising the manuscript for important intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript, participated in the study and questionnaire design, data analysis, drafted the manuscript, and approved it before submission.

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REFERENCES

- Bishop, C., Earp, J.A., Eng, E. & Lynch, K.S. (2002) Implementing a natural helper lay health advisor program: lessons learned from unplanned events. *Health Promotion Practice*; 3 (2), 233–244.
- Cnaan, R. A. & Goldberg-Glen, R. S. (1991). Measuring motivation to volunteer in human services. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 27, 269-284.
- Davis S. J. (1998) The 1997 National Survey of Volunteering in the UK. The National Centre for Volunteering, London.
- Davis S. J. (1999). Volunteering and social development: a background paper for discussion at an expert group meeting New York, October 1999. URL <http://www.unites.org>
- Drucker, P.F. (1992). Managing the Non-Profit Organization: Principles and Practices. Reprint edition. New York: HarperBusiness, (pages 3–49).
- Hall, P.A.. (1999). Social Capital in Britain. *British Journal of Political Science*. 29. 417 - 461. 10.1017/S0007123499000204.
- Henderson, K.A. (2018). Motivations and Perceptions of Volunteerism as a Leisure Activity, *Journal of Leisure Research*, 13 (3), 208-218
- Merrell J. (2000) ‘You don’t do it for nothing’: women’s experiences of volunteering in two community Well Woman Clinics. *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 8 (1), 31–39.
- Merrell J. (2000). ‘You don’t do it for nothing’: women’s experiences of volunteering in two community Well Woman Clinics. *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 8 (1), 31–39.
- Musick M.A., Herzog A.R. & House J.S. (1999) Volunteering and mortality among older adults: findings from a national sample. *The Journal of Gerontology*. Series B, Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences, 54 (3), S173–S180.
- Reitschlin J. (1998) Voluntary association membership and psychological distress. *Journal of Health & Social Behavior*, 39 (4), 348–355.
- Tang F. (2006) What resources are needed for volunteerism? A life course perspective. *Journal of Applied Grontology*, 25 (5), 375–390.
- Thoits P. & Hewitt L.N. (2001) Volunteer work and wellbeing. *Journal of Health & Social Behavior*, 42 (2), 115–131.
- Waters, R. D. (2010). The use of social media by nonprofit organizations: An examination from the diffusion of innovations perspective. In *Social computing: Concepts, methodologies, tools, and applications* (pp. 1420-1432). IGI Global.
- Wenger, S. (2004). Volunteers in the treatment program. Paradigm: 6–7, Summer 2000. www.onlineparadigm.com/archives/123-SOO_MH.AD.
- World Health Organization. Definition of Health, 1948.

Author Information

Aida Albasalah

Arabic Language Department, Arts College, Princes Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Alriyadh, Saudi Arabia

Samar Alshawwa

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, College of Pharmacy, Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Alriyadh, Saudi Arabia

Razan Alarnous

Child Development Center, King Abdullah bin Abdelaziz University Hospital, Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Alriyadh, Saudi Arabia
